

Water management

Irrigation schedule for dry season rice

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In Kerala, water is scarce during the later part of dry season (Sep-Jan). We laid out an experiment during the 1982 and 1983 dry seasons to test water conservation practices. The treatments are in the table.

Soil was sandy loam (79.3% sand, 7.8% silt, and 12.9% clay) with 1.27% organic C, 0.021% available N, 11.6 kg P/ha, and 184.4 kg K/ha; pH 5.5, and bulk density 1.045 g/cm³. Plot size was 7.0 × 2.2 m². Plots located on either side of the central irrigation channel had double bunds and 50 cm buffer strips all around. Five-cm-high pegs in the plots helped control irrigation water

Effect of water management practices on yield and water requirements of rice. ^a Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Treatment ^b	Yield (t/ha)		Water requirement (cm)	Irrigations (no.)
	Grain	Straw		
T ₁ = 5 cm submergence	3.7	4.5	92.6	33
T ₂ = 5 cm submergence 2 d after disappearance of ponded water.	3.5	4.6	63.7	11
T ₃ = T ₂ + 5 cm submergence for 7 d at panicle initiation and flowering.	3.5	4.6	69.1	18
T ₄ = 5 cm submergence to maximum tillering, followed by irrigation as in T ₂ .	3.5	4.5	64.0	16
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	12.3	8

^a Av of 2-yr.

applications.

The value of the water required for each irrigation was computed from the head difference and time of flow. Fluctuations in groundwater table were recorded weekly from a piezometer installed in the center of the field. The crop received 124.7 cm rainfall during growth. Irrigation treatments started after cessation of the northeast monsoon

and continued to 1 wk before harvest. The irrigation period lasted 65 d, with the groundwater table 102 cm below the surface.

Treatment 2 had grain and straw yields equal to those from 5 cm continuous submergence. It consumed 31% less water and required fewer irrigation. □

Water management studies in rice

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With the advent of high-yielding, short-statured rice varieties, the area under rice in Punjab (India) has increased from 0.57 million ha in 1975 to 1.7 million ha in 1987, increasing pressure on available water resources.

Standard practice is to flood rice beds with 10 cm water for 3 wk after transplanting, then apply 6-7 cm water 2 d after ponded water has infiltrated. We explored ways to reduce continuous deep flooding in 1985-87.

Rice variety PR106 was grown with three different water regimes during the rainy season (Jul-Oct) on loamy sand soil, alkaline, low-in available N, medium in available P and K. One-

Effect of duration of ponded water at transplanting on growth and yield of rice at Ludhiana (Punjab), India, 1987. ^a

Duration (wk)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Effective tillers/hill (no.)	Test wt (g/1000 grain)	Irrigation applied (cm)
1	6.4	6.6	86.7	8.9	22.6	195
2	6.5	6.7	86.6	8.8	22.9	215
3	6.5	6.7	87.0	9.1	22.9	235
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	—

^a Data pooled for 3 yr.

month-old seedlings were transplanted in 8- × 3-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. The crop was fertilized with 120 kg N, 26 kg P, 33 kg K, and 5.75 kg Zn/ha. Water was ponded at 40-50 mm depths for 1, 2, or 3 wk after transplanting. Standard irrigation

practice was used for later crop growth.

Reducing ponded water duration to 1 wk at transplanting did not adversely affect grain yield, straw yield, plant height, effective tillers, nor 1,000-grain weight (see table). It saved 40 cm water. □

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